

The physics of NHI UAP. A hypothetical framework of energy, propulsion, space-time travel and consciousness.

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“It shouldn’t be any more of a fact that extraterrestrials have come here than that we have gone to the Moon, ok? It’s just a part of the way things are and we have to understand it and put it in context of the story of ourselves, our knowledge base of cosmology, the nature of our existence, who we are, how the world works. And of course, that knowledge does change our understanding of how the world or the Universe at large works, because until the current period it was conventional wisdom both in science and theology that we’re alone in the Universe; the whole, single repository of life anywhere in the known Universe. Well, no one believes that anymore. That changes our concept of who we are and how we fit. And it’s becoming very clear that the way we have conducted ourselves as stewards of life on planet Earth is wanting, we haven’t been good stewards. We have environmental and global problems right now that are bringing civilization to a crisis and people do not want to hear that but it’s slowly becoming obvious that that is true. So this knowledge of who we are, how we manage the Planet, how we fit into the larger scheme of things is a very important question.”

Edgar Mitchell, astronaut and sixth man on the Moon

Introduction

Non-human intelligence seems to “admonish” us for not understanding time. According to them, reality, on a fundamental level, is in fact a continuous zero-point field-like instantaneous creation where time is no longer linear. In essence, only the instant now renewing itself at every interval is relevant, as both the past and the future always were and always will be.

Therefore, space-time travelers effectively could have access to the very matrix of creation. Reality may actually be determined to be a function of the Creator-consciousness in a perpetual self-actualization state. Time travel could even go so far in explaining, on a thanatological level, what occurs following biological death and even the metaphysics of reincarnation.

This begs the question, would extraterrestrial or interdimensional cultures a thousand or ten thousand years in the future not resolve all the riddles, paradoxes, and enigmas of physics and metaphysics? We should certainly hope so!

But how would one even begin investigating such a possibility on a scientific and ontological basis? Popular belief would have it that such phenomena lie well beyond the current scientific understanding, but further inquiry reveals quite possibly a wealth of theoretical and also practical data that could be used to support an introductory model.

First, we would need to have a basic grasp of the fundamental branches of physics that can be used to describe – at least in part – the various types of phenomena that have been observed for millennia; and secondly, a good grasp of the metaphysical aspect, insofar as to not get lost in needlessly rigid theory and abstract equations, or fall prey to mere “scientism”.

The main branches of physics that could be used to describe NHI technology are the following, in no particular order: electrodynamics (classical and stochastic), quantum mechanics (quantum field theory, quantum electrodynamics, quantum chromodynamics, quantum cosmology, chemistry and topology), classical mechanics (general relativity, special relativity), retrocausality, resonance and exotic metallurgy. At present there is no [available] theory to bridge the gap between all of these and form a unifying theory of physics, which could essentially unlock for us the secrets of space-time travel. This not what we are

attempting to do, but being little more than laymen, to compile whatever information is available and relevant to the question, for the betterment of the collective scientific and ontological understanding of the phenomena of non-human intelligence, and the types of physics that they might have mastered.

Figure 1. *The main branches of physics.* (Alfano, 2019)

Insofar as metaphysics are concerned, knowledge of philosophy, theology, esoterism and parapsychology (remote viewing, psychoenergetics) could be very useful in processing various aspects that cannot be properly integrated using current science and physics.

Historically, many technical reports over the span of the last eight decades have shown NHI UAP to be moving in ways that are not associated with any known propulsion systems, with speeds exceeding 68,000 km/h (Oberth, 1954) and in some cases transcending the concept of what would be considered “speed”, instead moving in a superluminal and/or non-local fashion. But classical physics tells us that no such speeds and means of transferring mass are possible, due to the laws of thermodynamics, gravity/inertia, as well the inadequacy of the materials science that is currently available.

The first law of thermodynamics (the conservation of energy) deals with an “indestructible” property of nature. This law essentially states that whatever amount of energy is expended as a force to perform work, equals, minus friction, the energy resulting from the work. Nothing is added or gained. Another way of saying it is that whatever you put into a mechanical process in the form of energy is what is returned, minus the friction loss coefficient of the operation. Under this law, you are never allowed to get back (from any known device) more energy than you put into it. In other words, a generator is actually an energy-converting device, not an energy-producing device, and is, therefore, not allowed to have an “over-unity” gain. The second law of thermodynamics states that all isolated physical systems unavoidably become more disordered in time (entropy), and explains why machines, supposedly, cannot keep running forever.

Throughout this work, we will see that there are indeed cases in which these laws and many others seem to be violated. Albeit a rather theoretical collection, we have identified some hypothetical but also practical examples that can be used to support this line of reasoning.

“Within a finite period of time past, the earth must have been, and within a finite period of time to come, the earth must again be, unfit for the habitation of man as at present constituted, unless operations have been or are to be performed, which are impossible under the laws to which the known operations going on at present in the material world, are subject.”
[William Thompson (Lord Kelvin)]

Lord Kelvin himself, subtly and perhaps begrudgingly, acknowledged a future possibility for a different outcome, in the form of laws yet unknown. These laws are inextricably interconnected with and dependent, in function, on other laws of physics and Nature; laws that once violated, have severe and revolutionary effects and enormous implications for the entire future foundations of humanity.

Kenneth Arnold’s 1947 sighting of a formation of disc-shaped craft, without any means of propulsion, flying at speeds well beyond what was possible during that period of history, suddenly brought to mankind’s collective consciousness the possibility, and then over time the probability, that life existed elsewhere in the universe, or here but in a different dimension, and was coming here in apparent total violation of general relativity and electrodynamics, such as they were understood back then.

“When I was at Wright-Patterson, we had the flying saucers that covered the distance from Columbus to Detroit in something like the equivalent of about 20,000 miles an hour. Back then, I don’t think anyone in the ordinary aerospace business would have had any knowledge of quantum physics or wormholes or the types of things we know now. But if you went to CERN now and talked to the particle physicists, they would tell you certainly, some of this was possible, because they see it all the time. Where they think they see mass, they really see energy frozen in a time quantum and what they’re seeing is really a frozen bundle of energy. It moves back and forth almost without any restriction.”
[Paul Czyzs, aerospace engineer]

“All the hypotheses are open. The phenomenon presents itself as a contact with space, in a large sense... with something outside of the Earth. That may be because everybody is expecting something in space. And when you speak to the witnesses, they are not describing something that comes from the sky. They are telling us that they’ve seen things disappear on the spot.”
[Jacques Vallee]

Chapter I. Matter and nonlocality. Is the speed of light absolute?

1.1. Matter

First, we could pose the question, “What is a solid object and where is the spatial boundary of a solid object?”

Classical physics would assume that boundary to be at its surface, but quantum field theory, quantum cosmology, and topology prove that:

1. The surface of material objects, meant as a smooth continual Riemannian manifold, does not exist (Gromov, 2007).
2. The boundary of a material object is related to the cosmologic model of choice (Linde, 2017).
3. The reasoning for the choice distinguishes a set of boundaries where the values of the function are allowed abrupt changes, and across which the adjacent regions cannot be connected. The common models of time and space are based on segmenting the set of real-valued numbers $\mathbf{R}^n$. They do not allow these possibilities because their boundaries’ topological structure is wrong (Alfano, 2019).

Where to set the boundaries is a decision defining the validity of the conclusions. The most comprehensive discussions of boundaries in quantum gravity were created by Esposito (1992). A very important Table 1 lists force fields corresponding to the alternative ways by which one group of charges can interact at a distance with another. The range of Coulomb and magnetic forces is limited but characterised by infinite propagation speed. (Alfano, 2019).

Force field	Acts on charges at rest?	Propagation speed	Long range?	Carrier
electric	yes	∞	no	n/a
magnetic	no	∞	no	n/a
radiation	yes	c	yes	photon

Table 1. *Infinite propagation speed of the electric and magnetic fields of force* (Alfano, 2019).

The energy density diverges as the boundary is approached, scaling down from boundaries at the infinity to the near-field region. This applies to the Standard Model interactions between photons and the fermionic matter composing detectors in the reactive near-field region around the matter, where all of the energy is negative, due to virtual particles popping in and out of existence (Alfano, 2019). This would suggest that, at the very least, our definition of solid objects is quite relative, depending on the cosmological model of choice, and that material objects might not – in specific circumstances at the very least – be so solid after all.

1.2. Nonlocality

Nonlocality is what Albert Einstein called ‘spooky action at a distance’ and it describes the ability of particles or objects to instantaneously know about each other’s state, even when separated by infinitely large distances, almost as if the Universe precognizes future events and “arranges” its particles accordingly. Thus, in the quantum Universe, notwithstanding

what Einstein had posited about the speed of light being absolute, instantaneous action or transfer of information does appear to be possible.

Experiments with quantum entanglement have shown the speed of ‘spooky action’ to be four orders of magnitude greater than the speed of light (Yin, 2013). This is in direct violation of what Einstein called the "principle of local action", or the idea that distant particles cannot influence each other at such scales, and that an object is directly influenced only by its immediate surroundings, an idea on which the greater part of physics is built upon. Nonlocality suggests that the Universe is quite different from our traditional understanding of it, and that the "separate" parts of the Universe might potentially be interconnected in ways that seems to transcend space-time.

We have already known from metaphysics and [some of] theology, for hundreds if not thousands of years, that all points in space-time are connected, a fact which seems to be increasingly supported by quantum field theory as well as parapsychology. Dr. Hermann Oberth theorized that NHI UAP utilize time/dimensional travel ships that don’t traverse large distances in space, but rather ‘jump’ from one time/space to another, or from one dimension to another and instantly back to their point of origin (Corso, 1998). It would not be altogether too difficult to envision this ‘jumping’ through space-time as some type of novel, macroscopic nonlocal or quantum phenomenon. Such phenomena of macroscopic scale have been observed and documented for some decades now, albeit in a very obscure and often secret manner, in various parapsychology experiments such as for example breaking through spatial barriers (Kongzhi, 1983) and psychokinesis (Gimeno, 2017).

As a side note, today we live immersed in a multitude of nonlocal engineering applications, aspects much more conventional than experimental physics or UFOs. Every time we use our credit cards in an ATM or for wireless payments in a POS, quantum electrodynamics assumes that the exchange of information between the card and the wireless system adopts nearly exclusively nonlocal space-like intermediate bosons. For over two centuries now, the same has also been true for all induction electric motors, for example (Alfano, 2019).

But how can Nature provide energy instantaneously? Multiple theories outline the way energy could propagate instantaneously, tunnelling without breaking causality, including the zero point-field and Nikola Tesla’s radiant energy, or what some call longitudinal magneto-dielectric scalar waves.

1.3. Light

The question of whether the speed of light is absolute has been a recurring theme for as long as it has been discovered, with the greater part of physics relying on the fact that it is indeed the case that c cannot be overcome, as was proven in multiple experimental endeavors and theoretical calculations. However, as the quantum world became better understood, this assumption began to be challenged in ways that are difficult for physicists to address even today.

On one hand, classical physics is very helpful for us in understanding how large bodies behave in space-time, such as planets and even human beings, while quantum mechanics teaches us how the building blocks of the Universe interact with each other at the extremely

minute scales. However, in the last decades, there has been a relative abundance of experiments in parapsychology which, although obscure and sometimes not peer reviewed, seem to really indicate that what we consider quantum phenomena may not, in fact, be confined to these very minuscule scales, but actually, under specific circumstances, become manifest in the macroscopic world as we know it.

In classical physics, light is described as a type of electromagnetic wave. The classical behaviour of the electromagnetic field is described by Maxwell's equations, which predict that the speed c with which electromagnetic waves (such as light) propagate in vacuum is related to the distributed capacitance and inductance of vacuum, also known as the electric constant ϵ_0 and the magnetic constant μ_0 , by the equation:

$$c = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}}.$$

In modern quantum mechanics, the electromagnetic field is described by the theory of quantum electrodynamics (QED). In this theory, light is described by the fundamental excitations (or quanta) of the electromagnetic field, called photons. In QED, photons are massless particles and thus, according to special relativity, they travel at the speed of light in vacuum.

We know from standard optical physics and quantum electrodynamics that the optical phase and group velocities can exceed c under certain physical conditions, but dispersion always ensures that the signal velocity is $\leq c$. But recent QED calculations (Scharnhorst, 1990; Latorre et al., 1995) have proved that in the Casimir Effect system, the dispersive effects are much weaker still than those associated with the increase in c so that the phase, group and signal velocities will therefore all increase by the same amount. Note that, in general, no dispersion shows up in all of the modified vacuum effects examined by investigators (Davis, 2004).

Vacuum quantum interactions with light lead to an effect on the speed of light that is due to the absorption of photons (by the vacuum) to form virtual electron-positron pairs followed by the quick re-emission (from the vacuum) of the photon. The virtual particle pairs are very short lived because of the large mismatch between the energy of a photon and the rest mass-energy of the particle pair. A key point is that this process makes a contribution to the observed vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 (and permeability μ_0) constant and, therefore, to the speed of light c [$c = (\epsilon_0 \mu_0)^{-1/2}$].

The role of virtual particle pairs in determining the ϵ_0 (μ_0) of the vacuum is analogous to that of atoms/molecules in determining the relative permittivity ϵ (and μ) of a dielectric material. We know that the absorption/re-emission of photons by atoms/molecules in a transparent medium (note: there are no strongly absorbing resonances, so the atoms/molecules remain in their excited states for a very short time before re-emitting photons) is responsible for the refractive index of the medium, which results in the reduction of the speed of light for photons propagating through the medium. This absorption/re-emission process is also known in physics as a scattering process. We know from experiment that a change in the medium leads to a change in ϵ (μ), thus resulting in a change of the refractive index. The key point arising from this analogy is that a modification of the vacuum

produces a change in ϵ_0 (μ_0) resulting in a subsequent change in c , and hence, a corresponding change in the vacuum refraction index (Davis, 2004).

Scharnhorst (1990) and Latorre et al. (1995) have since proved that the suppression of light scattering by virtual particle pairs (a.k.a. coherent light-by-light scattering) in the vacuum causes an increase in the speed of light accompanied by a decrease in the vacuum refraction index. This very unique effect is accomplished in a Casimir Effect capacitor cavity (or waveguide) whereby the vacuum quantum field fluctuations (a.k.a. zero-point fluctuations or ZPF) inside have been modified (becoming anisotropic and non-translational invariant) to satisfy the electromagnetic boundary conditions imposed by the presence of the capacitor plates (or waveguide walls). The principal result of this modification is the removal of the electromagnetic zero-point energy (ZPE) due to the suppression of vacuum ZPE modes with wavelengths longer than the cavity/waveguide cutoff ($\lambda_0 = 2d$, where d = plate separation). This removal of free space vacuum ZPE modes suppresses the scattering of light by virtual particle pairs, thus producing the speed of light increase (and corresponding decrease in the vacuum refraction index).

Davis (2004) also reports that a small number of $K < 1$ solutions were developed that describe FTL motion (i.e., c is increased, or the vacuum refraction index < 1 , when the modified vacuum has a lower energy density) which is generated by some distributed negative energy density such that the total energy density of the system as seen by remote observers is approximately zero. These solutions are similar in function to that of a traversable wormhole or warp drive effect (Alcubierre, 1994), which both arose from Einstein's General Relativity Theory and are both generated by distributed negative energy density in spacetime.

Tesla (1905) has also experimentally proven that longitudinal scalar waves, or radiant energy (then converted to electrical energy), can propagate at speeds exceeding c . Transmitter/receiver experiments with Faraday cages have shown that this effect can be verified by the fact that an electric and not a magnetic coupling is present, although the Faraday cage should shield electric fields. The scalar wave consequently overcomes the cage with a speed faster than light, by quantum tunnelling (Meyl, 2001; 2002).

*“The most essential requirement is, however, that
irrespective of frequency the wave or wave-train should continue
for a certain interval of time, which I have estimated to be not less than
one-twelfth or probably 0.08484 of a second and which is taken in passing to
and returning from the region diametrically opposite the pole over the earth's
surface with a mean velocity of about four hundred and seventy-one thousand
two hundred and forty kilometers per second” [471,240 km/sec; $\sim 1.5 \times c$].
(Nikola Tesla, 1905, US Patent #787412A)*

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 2. *Tesla's stationary waves generator (1905).*

Figure 3. *Apparatus for stationary waves recording (1905).*

In an endeavor to experimentally replicate Tesla's findings, Meyl (2001) has proven the following: the wireless transmission of electrical energy with an over-unity-effect of about 10, the reaction of the receiver to the transmitter, the transmission of scalar waves with 1.5 times the speed of light, and the inefficiency of Faraday cages in shielding from scalar waves. He goes on to note that Tesla's radiant energy is generally difficult to replicate due to fact that building a magnifying transmitter such as Tesla had is very expensive and that there is generally an absence of a suitable field description for scalar waves. Maxwell's equations only describe transverse waves, for which the field pointers oscillate perpendicular to the direction of propagation. He solved the former through the use of modern electronics, by replacing the spark gap generator with a function generator and the high tension operation with 2 - 4 Volts low tension; and the former by developing a mathematical model to match it, noting that the scalar wave part of the equation is actually the near-field effect of the antenna/transmitter (Meyl, 2001).

Meyl (2006) also notes that with the current RFID technology, the transfer of energy takes place on a chip card by means of longitudinal wave components, in close range of the transmitting antenna; and that those also are scalar waves, which spread towards the electrical or the magnetic field pointer. By conventional definition, radio frequency identification (RFID) uses electromagnetic fields to automatically identify and track tags attached to objects and it consists of a tiny radio transponder (tag), a radio receiver, and a transmitter.

Wave equation:

Laplace-operator	$\text{rot } \mathbf{E} = 0$ longitudinal wave	$\text{div } \mathbf{E} = 0$ transverse wave	$c =$ speed of light
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$$\Delta \mathbf{E} = \text{grad div } \mathbf{E} - \text{rot rot } \mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\delta^2 \mathbf{E}}{\delta t^2}$$

$\text{Div } \mathbf{E} \neq 0$ is a scalar $\Rightarrow$ **scalar wave!**

$\mathbf{E} = -\text{grad } \varphi$:

- (1) $\text{grad div } \mathbf{E} = -\text{grad } \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta t^2}$
- (2) $\text{div } \mathbf{E} = -\text{div grad } \varphi$

$\text{div } \mathbf{D} = \rho$:

- (3) $\text{div } \mathbf{E} = \rho/\epsilon$

plasma wave:

$$\Delta \varphi = \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\delta^2 \varphi}{\delta t^2} - \frac{\rho}{\epsilon}$$

i.e. = longitudinal Langmuir-wave
or: = longitudinal electric wave (vortex)

Figure 4. The scalar part of the wave equation describing longitudinal electric waves (Meyl, 2001)

Figure 5. Interpretation of scalar waves as an open resonant circuit (Meyl, 2001)

Chapter II. Quantum vacuum zero-point energy. Radiant energy.

So far, having (hopefully) established some starting ground for this discussion, it would now follow that for all the grand claims of space-time travel, there would be needed a corresponding source of energy that could theoretically sustain such a [until recently] science-fiction concept. The vacuum, as it turns out, may not be empty at all and could well represent a more than plentiful energy source for a highly advanced extra-terrestrial or inter-dimensional culture.

Milonni (1994) defined the vacuum as an integral component of both general relativity as well as quantum field theory, characterized by physical parameters and structure which constitute an energetic medium that pervades the entire Universe. According to quantum field theory, the Universe can be thought of not as isolated particles but continuous fluctuating fields: matter fields, whose quanta are fermions (i.e., leptons and quarks), and force fields, whose quanta are bosons (e.g., photons and gluons). All these fields have zero-point energy. (Milonni, 1994).

2.1. Zero-point energy

Historically and ideologically, zero-point energy evolved from much earlier concepts of the vacuum, the void, and what was eventually termed aether, concepts that for many hundreds, if not thousands of years, were strictly confined to philosophy and perhaps a few obscure and “unorthodox” practices. To Aristotle the vacuum was *τὸ κενόν*, or “*the empty*”; i.e., space independent of body. He believed this concept violated basic physical principles and asserted that the elements of fire, air, earth, and water were not made of atoms, but were continuous. To the atomists the concept of emptiness had absolute character: it was the distinction between existence and nonexistence (Saunders, 1991). The concept of zero-point energy was developed by Max Planck in Germany in 1911 as a correction added to a formula developed in his original quantum theory in 1900 (Kragh, 2012).

Within the context of general relativity theory, the vacuum is the seat of a spacetime structure (or metric) that encodes the distribution of matter and energy (Einstein, 1916). Within the context of quantum field theory, the vacuum is the seat of all energetic particle and field fluctuations; primary among them is the quantum vacuum electromagnetic zero-point energy (ZPE) or zero-point fluctuations/field (ZPF). The quantum vacuum ZPE is comprised of virtual particle pairs (i.e., electron-positron pairs or any other matter-antimatter particle pairs), which are very short lived because of the large discrepancy between the energy of a photon and the rest mass-energy of the virtual particle pair. In QFT a matter-antimatter particle pair annihilates with the result that their rest-mass energy is converted into a photon (Davis, 2004).

The term ‘zero-point energy’ is translated from *Nullpunktsenergie* in German. Sometimes used interchangeably with it are the terms zero-point radiation and ground state energy. The term zero-point field (ZPF) can be used when referring to a specific vacuum field, for instance the QED vacuum which specifically deals with quantum electrodynamics (e.g., electromagnetic interactions between photons, electrons and the vacuum) or the QCD vacuum which deals with quantum chromodynamics (e.g., color charge interactions between

quarks, gluons and the vacuum). A vacuum can be viewed not as empty space but as the combination of all zero-point fields. In quantum field theory this combination of fields is called the vacuum state, its associated zero-point energy is called the vacuum energy and the average energy value is called the vacuum expectation value (VEV), also called its condensate.

The energy density of the quantum vacuum electromagnetic ZPE is given by the gravity constant (G) and the characteristics of its particles are revealed by the cosmic microwave background (Massie, 2012). The energy density of ZPE is $\leq 10^{107} \text{J/cm}^3$ (Davis, 2004).

It should be noted here that the cosmological constant problem or vacuum catastrophe is the substantial disagreement between the observed values of vacuum energy density (the small value of the cosmological constant) and the much larger theoretical value of zero-point energy suggested by quantum field theory. Depending on the Planck energy cutoff and other factors, the quantum vacuum energy contribution to the effective cosmological constant is anywhere between 50 and as much as 120 orders of magnitude greater than observed, a situation described by physicists as *"the largest discrepancy between theory and experiment in all of science"* and *"the worst theoretical prediction in the history of physics"* (Adler, 1995). However, there are many physicists who believe that *"the vacuum holds the key to a full understanding of nature"* (Davies, 1985)

Davis (2004) warns that:

1. If one imposes a ZPE mode wavelength cutoff and takes ZPE mode interactions into account in the energy density calculation, then the result remains an enormous number.

2. One should ignore the heated technical debate between cosmologists/relativists and quantum field theorists over the reality of this number because there is presently no universally accepted theory that successfully bridges the gap between quantum field theory physics and spacetime physics.

3. Astrophysical observations indicating that the vacuum spacetime energy density is $\leq 10\text{--}15 \text{ J/cm}^3$ do not really measure the physical quantum vacuum energy density as claimed by cosmologists, but instead are really measuring the geometrical strain energy of spacetime due to the cosmological expansion of the universe.

"So called empty space isn't empty at all; it's actually full of energy. So instead of being like a quiet, empty lake, it's more like the froth at the base of a waterfall. This energy is basically electromagnetic in nature and the energy density is quite high. In fact, it's so high that when it was first discovered mathematically it was thought to be some kind of artifact of the mathematics. But then as time went on, there were even Nobel Prize winning experiments that showed that this energy and so called "empty" space was really there."
[Dr. Harold E. Puthoff, electrical engineer and physicist]

2.2. Methods for extracting zero-point energy

In 1948, Dutch physicists Hendrik B. G. Casimir and Dirk Polder predicted the existence of a tiny attractive force between closely placed metal plates due to resonances in the vacuum energy in the space between them. More precisely, the vacuum energy generated by the virtual particle pairs is pushing the plates together, and the vacuum energy between the plates is too small to negate this effect since fewer virtual particles can exist per unit volume between the plates than can exist outside them. This is now known as the Casimir effect and has since been extensively experimentally verified.

The vacuum ZPE can be exploited, via the Casimir Effect, for example, to extract electrical energy or actuate microelectromechanical devices (see for example, Ambjorn and Wolfram, 1983; Forward, 1984, 1996, 1998; Puthoff, 1990, 1993a; Cole and Puthoff, 1993; Milonni, 1994; Mead and Nachamkin, 1996; Lamoreaux, 1997; Chan et al., 2001).

Figure 6. Casimir Effect (d = cavity wall separation, λ = ZPF mode wavelength).

(Davis et al., 2006) give us another illustrative example of a scheme for extracting energy from the ZPF in the form of a patent by Mead and Nachamkin (1996). They propose that a set of resonant dielectric spheres be used to extract energy from the ZPF and convert it into electrical power. They consider the use of resonant dielectric spheres, slightly detuned from each other, to provide a beat-frequency downshift of the more energetic high-frequency components of the ZPF to a more easily captured form (see two embodiments of the invention in Figure 7). Their device includes a pair of dielectric structures (items 12, 14, 112, 114 in Fig. 7) that are positioned proximal to each other and which intercept incident ZPE radiation (items 16, 116 in Fig. 7). The volumetric sizes of the structures are selected so that they resonate at a particular frequency of the incident radiation. But the volumetric sizes of the structures are chosen to be slightly different so that the secondary radiation emitted from them (items 18, 20, 24, 118, 120, 124 in Fig. 7) at resonance interferes with each other, thus producing a beat frequency radiation that is at a much lower frequency than that of the incident radiation, and that can be converted into electrical energy. A conventional metallic antenna (loop or dipole type, or a RF cavity structure; items 22, 122 in Fig. 7) can then be used to collect the beat frequency radiation. This radiation is next transmitted from the antenna to a converter via an electrical conductor or waveguide (items 26, 126 in Fig. 7) and converted to electrical energy. The converter must include: 1) a tuning circuit or comparable

device so that it can effectively receive the beat frequency radiation, 2) a transformer to convert the energy to electrical current having a desired voltage, and 3) a rectifier to convert the energy to electrical current having a desired waveform (Davis et al., 2006)

Figure 7. ZPE Resonant Dielectric Spheres Electrical Power Generator (Mead & Nachamkin, 1996).

This research represents the baby steps that have been taken toward achieving a breakthrough in the extraction of significant useful energy from the vacuum. Nonetheless, a catalyst process that efficiently coheres and converts the ZPE into significant quantities of useful energy will be discovered in the near-future (Davis, 2004).

Is it therefore appropriate to suggest that a non human-intelligence should have had time enough to solve all such problems regarding the extraction of near-limitless energy from the vacuum?

2.3. Nikola Tesla’s radiant energy and scalar waves.

Of further interest for this chapter insofar as it could potentially be used by NHI as an energy source, would be what Nikola Tesla (1901) called “radiant energy” and which is defined, conventionally, as follows: the energy of electromagnetic and gravitational radiation. As energy, its SI unit is the joule (J). The quantity of radiant energy may be calculated by integrating radiant flux (or power) with respect to time.

Because electromagnetic radiation can be conceptualized as a stream of photons, radiant energy can be viewed as photon energy – the energy carried by these photons. Alternatively, EM radiation can be viewed as an electromagnetic wave, which carries energy in its oscillating electric and magnetic fields. These two views are completely equivalent and are reconciled to one another in quantum field theory and the dual wave-particle model.

Figure 8. *General arrangement of Apparatus for the Utilization of Radiant Energy (Tesla, 1901).*

We note here that radiant energy and longitudinal scalar waves might represent, in fact, the same phenomenon, or different aspects of the same phenomenon and may even play an important part in ZPE.

In his 1901 patent (US #685,957), Tesla goes on to describe radiant energy as follows: *“It is well known that certain radiations such as those of ultra-violet light, cathodic, Roentgen rays, or the like possess the property of charging and discharging conductors of electricity, the discharge being particularly noticeable when the conductor upon which the rays impinge is negatively electrified. These radiations are generally considered to be ether vibrations of extremely small wavelengths, and in explanation of the phenomena noted it has been assumed by some authorities that they ionize or render conducting the atmosphere through which they are propagated. My own experiments and observations, however, lead me to conclusions more in accord with the theory heretofore advanced by me that sources of such radiant energy throw off with great velocity minute particles of matter which are strongly electrified, and therefore capable of charging an electrical conductor, or even if not so, may at any rate discharge an electrified conductor either by carrying off bodily its charge or otherwise. My present application is based upon a discovery which I have made that when rays or radiations of the above kind are permitted to fall upon an insulated conducting-body connected to one of the terminals of a condenser, while the other terminal of the same is made by independent means to receive or to carry away electricity, a current flows into the condenser so long as the insulated body is exposed to the rays, and under the conditions hereinafter specified an indefinite accumulation of electrical energy in the condenser takes place.”*

Technically speaking, scalar waves have magnitude but no direction because they are imagined to be the result of two EM waves that are 180 degrees out of phase with each other, which leads to both signals being canceled out. This results in a kind of “pressure wave.” Mathematical physicist James Clerk Maxwell, in his original equations concerning electromagnetism, had established the theoretical existence of scalar waves. After his death, however, later physicists assumed these equations were meaningless and removed them, because they had not been empirically observed or proved experimentally; until Nikola Tesla, that is. Through longitudinal waves, Tesla transferred energy to receiving devices, he

transferred electrostatic forces through the air and noted the lethal forces produced by these waves.

Only the well-known (transverse) Hertzian waves can be derived from Maxwell's field equations, whereas the calculation of longitudinal SWs (scalar waves) gives zero as a result. This is a flaw of the field theory because scalar waves exist for all particle waves (e.g., as plasma wave, as photon or neutrino radiation). Starting from Faraday's discovery, instead of the formulation of the law of induction according to Maxwell, an extended field theory is derived. It goes beyond Maxwell's theory with the description of potential vortices (i.e., noise vortices) and their propagation as a SW, but contains Maxwell's theory as a special case. With that, the extension is allowed and does not contradict textbook physics (Zohuri, 2019).

In modern-day electrodynamics (both classical and quantum), electromagnetic waves traveling in "free space" (e.g., photons in the "vacuum") are generally considered to be transverse waves. But then again, this was not always the case. When the preeminent mathematician James Clerk Maxwell first modeled and formalized his unified theory of electromagnetism in the late nineteenth-century, neither the scalar longitudinal waves nor the electromagnetic transverse waves had been experimentally proved, but he had postulated and calculated the existence of both. After Hertz demonstrated experimentally the existence of transverse radio waves in 1887, theoreticians (e.g., Heaviside, Gibbs, and others) went about revising Maxwell's original equations; at this time, he was deceased and could not object. They removed the scalar wave component from the original equations because they felt that the mathematical framework and theory should be made to agree only with experiments. Evidently, the simplified equations worked — they helped make the AC/DC electrical age engineerable (Zohuri, 2019).

However, scalar waves did not ultimately go away because they are, after all, an integral part of the functioning of the Universe. Their unique properties can lead to more advanced application areas, with implications for surveillance systems, underwater imaging, energy production, power transmission, transportation, etc. This technology has the potential to transform communications, as well as electrodynamic applications in general.

According to Meyl (2012), scalar waves have yet other roles to play in areas which would not typically be associated with electromagnetism. He advances the theory that DNA generates longitudinal waves which propagate within the intercellular magnetic fields by means of magnetic scalar waves and that this theory explains how the dual base pair-stored information of the genetic code is formed, through the process of converting electrical modulation into "piggyback" information that transfers or is sent from the cell nucleus to another cell. Information transferred at the receiving end during the reverse process takes place involving a change in the physical and chemical cellular structure. He notes that the energy required to power the chemical process is now understood by the extended field theory to come from the magnetic scalar wave itself.

Besides Nikola Tesla, there have been developed a number of over-unity devices such as for example Thomas Henry Moray's radiant energy collector (ca. 1930). Dr. Moray developed a peculiar, germanium-based semiconductor he called a detector valve, which allowed power to flow through it one way but not the other, similar to but not identical to a modern diode.

He strung up a long, horizontal wire outside and ran one end through a series of oscillatory circuits containing his detector valves, then to a load – for example light bulbs – then to an earth ground. Dr. Moray could power a multiple kilowatt load with his device, which was witnessed by numerous engineers and scientists on multiple occasions. He felt his invention was tapping high frequency vibrations present in all space. The electricity which moved through his device had the characteristics of “cold electricity”, notably that it could flow along very thin wires and traverse small gaps in the wires separated by nonconductors like glass.

Figure 9. Comparison between the magnetic field and radiant energy waves.

The diagram above illustrates the difference between the magnetic field generated around a conductor fed with a pulse of direct current (DC) and the radiant energy waves created by that pulse. If a sharp current pulse is driven down a vertical wire, it causes two different types of fields. The first field is magnetic, where the lines of magnetic force rotate around the wire; these lines are horizontal, and rotate clockwise when viewed from above. The magnetic field remains as long as the current flows down the wire.

The second field is the radiant energy wave. This wave will only occur if the current pulse is in one direction, i.e. it will not occur if the wire is fed with alternating current. The wave radiates out horizontally from the vertical wire in every direction in the form of a shock wave. It is a one-off event and does not repeat if the current in the wire is maintained. The radiant energy briefly unbalances the zero-point energy field and that causes an energy flow as the field moves back into equilibrium again. The radiant energy wave is not restricted to a single plane as shown in the diagram above, which is intended to indicate the difference between the electromagnetic field circling around the wire, and the radiant energy field which radiates away from the wire. Both of these fields occur at all points along the full length of the wire, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 10. Different perspectives of radiant energy propagating through a conductor.

Radiant energy, when converted to electrical power, produces a different kind of electrical energy to that produced by generators. Power a motor with conventional electricity and it gets hot under load. Power the same motor by radiant energy converted to electricity and under load the motor gets cold. Really overload it and the motor housing is likely to get covered with frost. That is why this form of electricity is referred to as "cold" electricity.

This may suggest that in extreme situations involving the production of high energies at very specific frequencies, there might be some cracks exposed in the alleged “impenetrable” monolithic fortress of classical/quantum electrodynamics, implying possible key missing theoretical and physical elements. Unfortunately, some of these experimental phenomena have been difficult to replicate and produce on-demand. More over, some have been shown apparently to violate some of the established principles underlying classical thermodynamics (Zohuri, 2019).

Lyne (1998) offers some more insights into Tesla’s research that enforce the idea that radiant energy and the ZPF might be connected. The existence of the ZPE was well known to Tesla in the 1890s, but it was not until recently that it became scientifically accepted as a proven fact. He called it the ‘ether’/‘aether’ and concluded that it is a radiation of such high frequency that it normally passes through space, the earth, and our bodies without harm or incident, in constant equilibrium, because its short wavelengths do not normally react or resonate with the atoms of most matter.

“Nature has stored up in the universe infinite energy. The eternal recipient and transmitter of this infinite energy is the ether. The recognition of the existence of ether, and of the functions it performs, is one of the most important results of modern scientific research. The mere abandoning of the idea of action at a distance, the assumption of a medium pervading all space and connecting all gross matter, has freed the minds of thinkers of an ever present doubt, and, by opening a new horizon—new and unforeseen possibilities—has given fresh interest to phenomena with which we are familiar of old.”

Nikola Tesla, 1891

Although at times in disagreement with each other, Einstein himself had concluded the existence of the aether, and implicitly of radiant energy, in 1920, and expanded on his views in 1922 and 1924.

"How does it come about that alongside of the idea of ponderable matter, which is derived by abstraction from everyday life, the physicists set the idea of the existence of another kind of matter, the ether? The explanation is probably to be sought in those phenomena which have given rise to the theory of action at a distance, and in the properties of light which have led to the undulatory theory".

Albert Einstein, 1922

It is radioactive matter, according to Tesla, which has a peculiar atomic structure which reacts with this radiation (aether, ZPF) to produce radioactivity. Atomic energy, to Tesla, came from the ZPE and not atoms. If a lump of radium could be shielded from the effects of the ZPE, said Tesla, it would show no radioactivity.

Most naturally radioactive elements are dense and unstable, that is, they are said by the relativists to decay as radiation is emitted, to elements of lower atomic numbers. The relativists, with whom Tesla vehemently disagreed, believe that naturally radioactive elements spontaneously lose mass in the process of such decay, so that the energy released as radioactivity, is equivalent to the lost mass according to Einstein's equation, $E=mc^2$.

In a New York Times article of July 11, 1937 (pg.13, col.2), in one of Tesla's famous birthday announcements, Tesla stated that he had developed a process for the manufacture of radium (transmutation from other elements), which was so efficient that it could be sold for \$1.00 per pound. He also announced that he had developed a system for the interstellar transmission of energy. He said he had been working in several laboratories, but refused to disclose their locations. His working model, he said,

"...employs more than three dozen of my inventions. It is a complex apparatus, an agglomeration of parts. It could convey several thousand units of horsepower to other planets, regardless of the distance. Traveling through a channel of less than one-half of one-millionth of a centimeter...This is not an experiment. I have built, demonstrated and used it. Only a little time will pass before I can give it to the world." O'Neill (1994) offers us more context:

"I am now planning aerial machines devoid of sustaining planes, ailerons, propellers and other external attachments, which will be capable of immense speeds and are very likely to furnish powerful arguments for peace in the near future. Such a machine, sustained and propelled entirely by reaction, can be controlled either mechanically or by wireless energy. By installing proper plants it will be practicable to project a missile of this kind into the air and drop it almost on the very spot designated which may be thousands of miles away. But we are not going to stop at this..."

It will be noted here that there exist some anecdotal accounts which would suggest that Nikola Tesla had known about non-human intelligence, in some shape or form. It is impossible to establish the truthfulness of such claims but we feel that this hypothesis should not be left out of this work, even if only as an entertaining 'what if'.

We also note here that there are some propulsion and energy generation models based on nuclear fusion, for example Gary Gochnour's inventions (2006, 2008) that could also potentially be considered a viable source of energy for NHI craft.

Figure 11. Cross section side view of multi-functional high-energy plasma aircraft (Gochnour, 2008).

The figure above is showing a side view of a multi-functional high-energy plasma aircraft and nuclear fusion system (US Patent #2008/0061191A1), containing an ion acceleration system, a central shaft containing an inductance coil, annular bladed ring assembly, capacitor system, electrolysis system, crew cabin doors for access to upper deck and lower deck through said central shaft, crew hatch doors for entering or exiting craft through the central shaft, and a pilot area and pilot aircraft controls, and an engineer area and diagnostic controls for plasma and electric systems (Gochnour, 2008)

Chapter III. Gravity and anti-gravity. Electrogravitic and gravitomagnetic propulsion.

Having established three potential energy sources for our would-be extraterrestrial or interdimensional neighbours, the question follows of how one would go about “engineering” gravity in order to create an anti-gravitic effect that would lift a craft and “propel” it through space-time. First, it is necessary to have a decent grasp of what gravity and negative energy are, within the current understanding.

3.1. Gravity

General relativity postulates a relationship between mass and energy and the structure of spacetime that exerts real physical effects called gravity, where massive objects, made of elementary particles making up their mass, curve spacetime resulting in a gravitational force. However, application of the same principles at the subatomic level yields gravitational forces that are so infinitely small that they are found to be insignificant. Yet, at the proton nuclear scale, extremely large confining forces are found which would require extremely high energy levels (or masses) to produce such a force in the context of general relativity. In fact, those very high levels of energy were actually predicted by early QFT resulting in the so-called ‘bare mass’ of particles but renormalized by modern QED (Quantum electrodynamics) and QCD (Quantum chromodynamics), utilizing quantum vacuum fluctuations as a shielding mechanism (Milonni, 2019). Consequently, one could ask the question in a different way than generally approached; that is, instead of why gravity is so weak, which has no meaning at the quantum level, asking why is the proton mass, which makes up most of the mass of the material world, so small? This change in reasoning was eventually mentioned by others such as Franck Wilczek (2001). Furthermore, from advanced study of QFT and the divergence of bare mass, one can ask a more fundamental question: are quantum vacuum fluctuations responsible for the bare mass shielding or are they themselves the source of mass and the resulting forces? (Haramain et al., 2023)

The general idea that mass is some kind of immutable constant, independent of force and energy, was dispelled in the early twentieth century by the discovery of special and general relativity, when it was concluded that there is a fundamental equivalence between the concept of mass, energy and the geometry of space-time. General relativity establishes fundamental gravitational forces, which aggregate particles and organized matter such as galaxies, stars, solar systems and planets, as the result of the curvature of the structure of space-time itself. However, this curvature results from an undefined source of energy, called mass, emerging from quantum entities we called particles. On the other hand, we have developed theories that describe these particles and energy structures as quantities emerging from very high energetic fields resulting from a fundamental oscillation of space itself, which we call quantum vacuum fluctuations. These fields of ‘virtual’ particles are at the basis of

many of our modern particle theories of QFT, one of them being the Higgs field (Haramain et al., 2023).

Sakharov (1968) also suggested that gravity might be an induced effect brought about by changes in the zero-point energy state of the vacuum, due to the presence of matter. Puthoff (1989a, b, 1993b) developed a model whereby the gravitational interaction begins with a particle situated in the sea of electromagnetic ZPF developing a “jitter” motion (a.k.a. *Zitterbewegung*). When there are two or more particles they are each influenced not only by the fluctuating background electromagnetic field, but also by the electromagnetic fields generated by the other particles, all similarly undergoing *Zitterbewegung* motion, and the inter particle coupling due to these fields results in the attractive gravitational force. Gravity can thus be understood as a kind of long-range Casimir force. The major benefit of Puthoff’s approach is that it provides a basis for understanding various characteristics of the gravitational interaction hitherto unexplained. These include the relative weakness of the gravitational force under ordinary circumstances (shown to be due to the fact that the coupling constant G depends inversely on the large value of the high-frequency cutoff of the ZPF spectrum); the existence of positive but not negative mass and the fact that gravity cannot be shielded (a consequence of the fact that quantum ZPF “noise” in general cannot be shielded). If this model is correct, then it would be possible to alter or modify gravity by affecting the vacuum ZPE (Davis, 2004).

A potential connection between the ZPF and inertia was first published by Haisch et al. (1994). If accurate, this would suggest that mass and gravity could be an electromagnetic phenomenon and thus in principle subject to modification, with vast technological implications for propulsion and indeed, why not, space-time travel.

*“If people are here from another civilization,
then they’ve understood the finer points of quantum physics.”
[Dr. Paul Czyzs, aerospace engineer]*

3.2. Negative energy and anti-gravity.

Negative or “exotic” energy is a concept used in physics to explain the nature of certain fields, including the gravitational field and various quantum field effects. It is an acceptable result both mathematically and physically in GR and QFT and it manifests gravitational repulsion or antigravity (Davis, 2004).

The exotic (energy condition-violating) mass-energy fields that are known to occur in nature are:

- Radial electric or magnetic fields. These are borderline exotic, if their tension were infinitesimally larger, for a given energy density (Herrmann, 1989; Hawking and Ellis, 1973).
- Squeezed quantum states of the electromagnetic field and other squeezed quantum fields; see the following sections for a discussion on squeezed quantum states (Morris and Thorne, 1988; Drummond and Ficek, 2004).

- Gravitationally squeezed vacuum electromagnetic zero-point energy; see the next three sections for the discussion on squeezed quantum states (Hochberg and Kephart, 1991).
- Casimir Effect energy in flat or curved spaces (DeWitt, 1975; Birrell and Davies, 1984; Saunders and Brown, 1991; Milonni, 1994; Milton, 2001). Other quantum fields/states/effects. In general, the local energy density in quantum field theory can be negative due to quantum coherence effects (Epstein, Glaser and Jaffe, 1965).
- Other examples that have been studied are Dirac field states: the superposition of two single particle electron states and the superposition of two multi-electron-positron states (Vollick, 1998; Yu and Shu, 2003).
- Cosmological inflation, cosmological particle production, classical scalar fields, the conformal anomaly and gravitational vacuum polarization are among many other examples that also violate the energy conditions (Davis, 2010).

Negative energy could be used to produce antigravity for the simplest case of counteracting the Earth’s gravitational field. To counteract or otherwise reduce gravity merely requires the deployment of a thin spherical shell (bubble) of negative energy around an aerospace vehicle (Davis, 2010).

Figure 12. *Negative energy bubble around a spacecraft.* (Davis, 2004)

As an interesting side note, a Universe in which positive energy dominates will eventually collapse in a “big crunch”, while an “open” Universe in which negative energy dominates will either expand indefinitely or eventually disintegrate in a “big rip”. In the zero-energy universe model (“flat” or “Euclidean”), the total amount of energy in the universe is exactly zero: its amount of positive energy in the form of matter is exactly cancelled out by

its negative energy in the form of gravity (Hawking, 2010). There is currently no consensus on which of these models – if any – accurately describes the real universe, but it would not be wrong to assume that NHI has developed a better model than us, perhaps a non-linear one that is not fated to end in either a ‘big crunch’ or a ‘big rip’.

As for antigravity induced through ZPF force, Calloni et al. (2002) propose an experimental device that could significantly magnify the repulsive force up to a measurable scale. Their proposed device is a multilayered series of rigid Casimir cavities with each cavity consisting of two thin metallic disks that are separated by a dielectric material which is inserted to maintain rigidity. They suggest SiO₂ for the dielectric material because it is an efficient dielectric with low absorption over a wide range of frequencies, and it is an inexpensive material that is easy to fabricate into layers. Calloni et al. propose to magnify the total force by using $N_t=10^6$ layers of rigid cavities with each cavity having a diameter of 35 cm and thickness of 100 nm, for a total device thickness of 10 cm. They estimate that doing this could produce a force $F_{CGexp}= 10^{14}$ N (where F_{CGexp} is the gravitational repulsion coefficient) at a modulation frequency on the order of tens of mHz for $d = 5$ nm. This result is more than two orders of magnitude larger than the force which the VIRGO gravitational wave antenna is expected to detect at several tens of Hz.

Davis (2010) concludes that antigravity forces produced by quantum electromagnetic vacuum ZPF in a curved spacetime (that is, gravitational field) are very feeble, but there are proposals based on other theoretical and empirical studies which suggest that these forces can be amplified to macroscopic level.

3.3. Electrogravitic and electrokinetic propulsion

What is electrogravitics? Valone (2012) gives us the definition as follows: “electricity used to create a force that depends upon an object’s mass, even as gravity does”. This definition may identify true electrogravitics, when the object’s mass linearly affects the resultant force, in conjunction with a dielectric. This is also what the “*Biefeld-Brown effect*” of Townsend Brown’s first patent (British #300,311) describes.

Thomas Townsend Brown was a physics student of Dr. Paul Alfred Biefeld at the California Institute for Advanced Studies. Brown noticed that when he had two plates carrying high voltages of direct current separated by a dielectric, the negative electrode moved by itself in the direction of the positive plate. In other words, Townsend Brown discovered that it is possible to create an artificial gravity field by charging an electrical capacitor to a high-voltage.

He built a special capacitor which utilized a heavy, high charge-accumulating (high K-factor) dielectric material between its plates and found that when charges with between 70,000 to 300,000 volts, it would move in the direction of its positive pole. When oriented with its positive side up, it would proceed to lose about one percent of its weight. He attributed this motion to an electrostatically-induced gravity field acting between the capacitor’s oppositely charged plates. By 1958, he had succeeded in developing a 15 inch diameter model saucer that could lift over 110% of its weight. Brown’s experiments had launched a new field of investigation which came to be known as electrogravitics, the technology of controlling gravity through the use of high-voltage electric charge. As early as 1952, an Air Force major

general witnessed a demonstration in which Brown flew a pair of 18 inch disc airfoils suspended from opposite ends of a rota-table arm. When electrified with 50,000 volts, they circuted at a speed of 12 miles per hour. About a year later, he flew a set of 3 foot diameter saucers for some Air Force officials and representatives from a number of major aircraft companies. When energized with 150,000 volts, the discs sped around the 50 foot diameter course so fast that the subject was immediately classified.

Interavia magazine later reported that the discs could attain speeds of several hundred miles per hour when charged with several hundred thousand volts. Brown's discs were charged with a high positive voltage, on a wire, running along their leading edge and a high negative voltage, on a wire, running along their trailing edge. As the wires ionized the air around them, a dense cloud of positive ions would form ahead of the craft and corresponding cloud of negative ions would form behind the craft. Brown's research indicated that, like the charged plates of his capacitors, these ion clouds induced a gravitational force directed in the minus to plus direction. As the disc moved forward in response to its self generated gravity field, it would carry with it its positive and negative ion clouds and their associated electrogravity gradient. Consequently, the discs would ride their advancing gravity wave much like surfers ride an ocean wave.

Figure 13. Electrogravitic craft demonstration unit (McCandlish, 2000).

Valone (2012) considers electrogravitics as having historically had a purported relationship to gravity or the object's mass, as well as the applied voltage. An analysis of the 90-year old science of electrogravitics (or electrogravity) must include an analysis of electrokinetics. Electrokinetics is more commonly associated with many patents of T. Townsend Brown as well as Agnew Bahnsen, starting with the 1960 US patent #2,949,550 entitled, "*Electrokinetic Apparatus*". Electrokinetics, which often involves a capacitor and dielectric and has virtually no relationship that can be connected with mass or gravity. It is noted here that subsequent T. Townsend Brown patents never mention electrogravitics but

rather, later on, Brown refers to “electrokinetics” (logically, a subset of electrogravitics), which also uses asymmetric capacitors to amplify the force.

Incidentally, Brown also became involved in the subject of unidentified flying objects (UFOs) and, in 1956, helped found the National Investigations Committee On Aerial Phenomena (NICAP), although he was forced out as director in 1957 with rumours that he was using funds to further anti-gravity research.

Another similar invention with comparable experiments that involve the negation of gravity is called “gravitational anisotropy” and was developed by Rudolf G. Zinsser from Germany. Zinsser discovered that if he connected his patented pulse generator to two conductive metal plates immersed in water, he could induce a sustained force that lasted even after the pulse generator was turned off. The pulses lasted for only a few nanoseconds each (Cravens, 1994). Zinsser called this input a “kinetobaric driving impulse” and furthermore pointed out in the Specifications and Enumerations section, that the high dielectric constant of water (about 80) is desirable and that a solid dielectric is possible. Dr. Peschka (1974; 1998) calculated that Zinsser’s invention produced 6 Ns/Ws or 6 N/W. This figure is *twenty times* the force per energy input of the Inertial Impulse Engine of Roy Thornson, which has been estimated to produce 0.32 N/W. By comparison, it is important to realize that any production of force today is extremely inefficient, as seen by the fact that a DC-9 jet engine produces only 0.016 N/W or 3 lb/hp, while fossil-fuel-powered land and air vehicles are even worse (Valone, 1993; 2012).

Brown (1929) also refers to the “endogravitic” and “exogravitic” times that were representative of the charging and discharging times. Once the gravitator was charged, depending upon “its gravitic capacity” any further electrical input had no effect. This is the same phenomenon that Zinsser witnessed and both agree that the pulsed voltage generation was the main part of the electrogravitic effect (McCandlish, 1988). Both Zinsser and Brown worked with dielectrics and capacitor plate transducers to produce the electrogravitic force. Both refer to a high dielectric constant material in between their capacitor plates as the preferred type to best insulate the charge. However, Zinsser never experimented with different dielectrics nor higher voltage to increase his force production. (Valone, 2012).

Interestingly enough, Brown and Zinsser’s experimental electrogravitics/electrokinetics also showed that there are associated effects on plants and animals, as well as effects from the sun, moon and even slightly from some of the planetary positions. Zinsser also reports beneficial effects on plants and humans, including what he called “*bacteriostasis and cytostasis*” (Valone, 2000).

We note that of general interest for any and all kinds of electrical equipment and devices, including – at least some – UAP, are conductors and especially superconductors. Some experimental research has been done in this area by Li and Torr (1991, 1993) showing that the carriers of quantized angular momentum in superconductors are not the Cooper pairs but the lattice ions, and further that the coherent alignment of lattice ion spins will generate a detectable gravitomagnetic field, and in the presence of a time-dependent applied magnetic vector potential field, a detectable gravitoelectric field.

Next, we will take a look at yet another electrokinetic model, John St. Clair's "*Triangular spacecraft*" (US Patent #2006/0145019A1). While St. Clair doesn't overtly refer to his invention as an electrogravitic or electrokinetic spacecraft, the diagrams and explanations he offers would seem to suggest that.

St. Clair describes his invention as a triangular hull spacecraft having vertical electrostatic line charges on each corner. The line charges create a horizontal electric field that, together with a plane wave emitted by antennas on the side of the hull, generates a force per Volume providing a unique combination of both lift and propulsion. An array of horizontal slot antennas emit electromagnetic waves that have a vertically polarized electric E field. These traveling waves then interact with the electric field produced by the line charges on the corners of the triangle to provide a lift and propulsion effect.

Figure 14. Perspective view of triangular spacecraft (St. Clair, 2006).

A parabolic antenna (**E**) is centrally located in the bottom of the hull. An array of horizontal slot antennas is located along the side of the hull (**A**). Each back corner (**F,G**) has a conducting plate which is charged to a positive voltage $+V$ while the forward corner (**C**) has a conducting plate charged to a negative voltage $-V$. The 60° angle on the corner creates a line charge density singularity that produces a huge horizontal electric field pointing from the back to the front of the craft which is also parallel to the sides of the triangle. An array of horizontal slot antennas located on the sides of the triangular hull produce an electromagnetic wave with the electric field polarized in the vertical direction. This combination of fields produces a spacetime force in both the vertical and horizontal directions such that the spacecraft receives a lift force and a force of propulsion. A motion control hemisphere (**D**) is located on the bottom surface in each of the three corners.

Figure. 15. *2D graph of the electric fields produced by three line charges on the corners of the triangular hull. (St. Clair, 2006)*

Chapter IV. Space-time travel, retrocausality and vacuum engineering.

*“What is space? An empty stage where the physical world
of matter acts out its drama? An equal participant that
both provides background and has a life of its own?
Or the primary reality of which matter is a secondary manifestation?
Views on this question have evolved, and several times
have changed radically, over the history of science.
Today the third view is triumphant.”
[Frank Wilczek]*

Albert Einstein had established long ago, through general relativity, that space and time are inextricably connected to one another. Therefore, to travel in space is to travel in time. The author is however of the opinion that if NHI is indeed adept at the finer points of quantum physics and possesses a more complete physical model of reality than us, then it might be possible for them, hypothetically, to separate space from time, at least in our three dimensional and linear Universe as we perceive it.

4.1. Time travel and retrocausality.

Some theories, most notably special and general relativity, suggest that suitable geometries of space-time or specific types of motion in space might allow time travel into the past and future if these geometries or motions were possible (Thorne, 1994). In theoretical papers, physicists discuss the possibility of closed timelike curves, which are world lines that form closed loops in spacetime, allowing objects to return to their own past. There are known to be solutions to the equations of general relativity that describe spacetimes which contain closed timelike curves, such as Gödel spacetime, but the physical plausibility of these solutions is uncertain.

A great deal of the subject of time-travel is “burdened” by the ‘grandfather paradox’, but if one considers, for example, the many-worlds interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics, many of the inherent issues would be resolved; this interpretation is similar to the Novikov self-consistency principle. The many-worlds interpretation isolates the past of a system from its future evolution, tracing over everything apart from the events composing the space-time region of the would-be stargate/wormhole entrance. Swartz (1993) argues that time-travel is possible but that it would be impossible to actually change the past in any way.

*“UFO reports are not necessarily caused by
visits from space travelers....If time and space
are not as simple in structure as physicists have
assumed until now, then the question ‘where do they
come from?’ may be meaningless: they could come from
a place in time.”
[Jacques Vallee]*

A variation of Hugh Everett's many-worlds interpretation (MWI) of quantum mechanics provides a possible solution to the grandfather paradox which would involve the time traveler arriving in a different Universe or dimension than the one they came from; it's been argued that since the traveler arrives in a different Universe's history and not their own 'continuum', this is not "genuine" time travel (Arntzenius, Maudlin; 2009). The consensus many-worlds interpretation suggests that all possible quantum events occur in mutually exclusive histories (Vaidman, 2014).

We note that there is also a distinct possibility that hypothetical travelers from a different timeline might be able to interact with other beings from other timelines/dimensions only insofar as the said interaction would not significantly and causally alter the timeline of the destination (ie: no actions would result from the interaction which would significantly alter events in the future). This could suppose a 'liminal' and temporary state of energy/matter in which such interactions might take place, but also that once that state ends, the being in the destination timeline would resume the normal 'continuum' and forget, as it were, that anything happened, so as to not possibly alter the future in any significant way. This would heavily involve the metaphysical concept of free will. A possible solution to this could be that the being in the destination timeline (ie. the one who is being visited) would be able to "resist" the causal impulse that would normally be effected by such an interaction and therefore, consciously and of his own accord, not act in any way that might significantly alter the causality of his own Universe and therefore violate free will.

As far as retrocausality, or rather, a reversal of the flow of time, recent research has shown the possibility of our Universe having arisen, both classically and quantum mechanically, from a parallel but mirrored Universe that existed before the Big – Bang and in which time flows backwards (Boyle et al., 2002). They proposed that, in this way, the Universe does not spontaneously violate CPT (Charge, Parity, and Time reversal symmetry).

The matter that is present in one universe could be seen, from the perspective of the other universe, as antimatter, and viceversa. They thus form a pair and from a global point of view, the creation in pairs of universes-antiuniverses restores the matter-antimatter asymmetry observed in every individual universe and it could provide us with insights into the whole multiverse theory. The idea of a time reversal relation between a pair of universes to explain the matter-antimatter asymmetry observed in our universe is not new, but dates back at least to the early 70's and it was even proposed by Sakharov in the early 80's (Robles-Perez, 2020).

More than seventy years ago, Richard Feynman and Ernst Stueckelberg developed an alternative interpretation of the positron as an electron moving back in time, in a reinterpretation of the negative-energy solutions of the Dirac equation. Retrotemporal or backwards moving electrons would have a positive electric charge (Feynman, 1949). The reversal of antiparticles is in fact required in modern QFT and also plays a part in how nucleons are bound together with the nuclear force, via the exchange of virtual mesons (a meson is made up of an equal number of quarks and anti-quarks, bound together by the strong force). In a telephone call to Richard Feynman from the spring of 1940, Wheeler first told Feynman about the hypothesis that all electrons and positrons are actually the

manifestations of a single entity moving backwards and forwards in time. Later, Yoichiro Nambu applied this hypothesis to all production and annihilation of particle-antiparticle pairs, stating that *"the eventual creation and annihilation of pairs that may occur now and then is no creation or annihilation, but only a change of direction of moving particles, from past to future, or from future to past."* (Nambu, 1950)

4.2. Stargates and wormholes.

Davis (2010) asserts that since the laws of quantum field theory place no strong restrictions on negative energies and fluxes then it might be possible to produce exotic phenomena such as faster-than-light travel, traversable wormholes, violations of the second law of thermodynamics and time machines. He gives us the following methods/descriptions of teleportation:

- Engineering the vacuum or spacetime metric: the conveyance of persons or inanimate objects across space by altering the properties of the spacetime vacuum, or by altering the spacetime metric (geometry). We will call this vm-Teleportation.
- Quantum entanglement: the disembodied transport of the quantum state of a system and its correlations across space to another system, where system refers to any single or collective particles of matter or energy such as baryons (protons, neutrons, etc.), leptons (electrons, etc.), photons, atoms, ions, etc. We will call this q-Teleportation.
- Exotic: the conveyance of persons or inanimate objects by transport through extra space dimensions or parallel universes. We will call this e-Teleportation.
- Psychic: the conveyance of persons or inanimate objects by psychic means. We will call this p-Teleportation.

A traversable stargate is essentially a tunnel through space-time connecting an entrance portal to an exit portal, with the portals not possessing an event horizon and the tunnel not possessing a singularity (Thorne and Morris, 1988). It is possible that man-made wormholes can be engineered to keep the gravitational tidal forces to a comfortable minimum. Natural wormholes may be detected by astronomical searches for the gravitational lens effect they induce on background star light (Cramer et al., 1995). If the conditions for wormholes exist in space, it may be possible to detect and eventually confirm their existence. In any case, we have some insight into techniques for artificially generating small wormholes which, according to present understanding, could in principle be used to send information faster than the speed of light, and perhaps eventually vehicles and beings as well. (Davis, 1998; Van Flinders, 1998).

There would be no real FTL motion involved when traveling through a traversable stargate. That is because stargates are a 'hyperspace' shortcut through the universe, whereby space travelers can traverse enormous astronomical distances within a matter of a few minutes or days while traversing only a few meters or kilometers through the throat/tunnel (Davis, 2004). Stargates/wormholes can even connect together different space-time dimensions. Wormholes can possess normal or backwards (in special cases) time flow, normal or nonexistent gravitational stresses on space travelers, and their entry/exit openings (or

throats) can be spherically shaped, cubic shaped, polyhedral shaped, or generic shaped, etc. A byproduct of wormhole studies has been the development of wormholes possessing flat entry/exit openings (Davis, 2004).

A thin shell of negative (i.e., “exotic”) energy must be distributed locally in order to generate the wormhole geometry. It has been shown (Visser, 1995; Davis, 2004) that the amount of negative energy required to create and stabilize a 1-meter radius wormhole throat is $-0.71 M_J$ ($M_J = 1.90 \times 10^{27}$ kg, the mass of planet Jupiter). However, Visser et al. (2003) demonstrated the existence of spacetime geometries containing traversable wormholes that are supported by arbitrarily small quantities of negative energy, and they proved that this was a general result.

Davis (2004) concluded that a traversable wormhole can be envisioned to facilitate ETO (Earth to orbit) transportation via a portal that connects a location on the Earth’s surface with a location in LEO (low-Earth orbit), GEO (geostationary orbit) or elsewhere. He has also theoretically shown two practically equivalent ways to implement vm-Teleportation, through the manipulation of spacetime geometry via exploiting negative (i.e., quantum vacuum zero point) energy as shown by Einstein’s general relativity theory, and the modification of the vacuum dielectric constant as shown by the PV-GR (Polarizable vacuum-general relativity) model. He concluded that both have a great deal of theoretical foundation to begin exploring experimentally.

Besides what Davis (2004) calls vm-Teleportation, such as stargates or engineering the vacuum, we would suggest that there have been experiments in parapsychology that would seem to also confirm the existence of p-teleportation, or psychic space-time teleportation, in the form of coordinate remote viewing (McMoneagle, 1984).

Figure 16. Diagram for a traversable wormhole.

Levi-Civita (1917), more than a hundred years ago, also predicted the possibility of inducing space-time curvatures through generating a uniform static magnetic or electric field (possessing cylindrical symmetry) to create an artificial gravitational field in accordance with general relativity (Pauli, 1981). Davis (1998, 1999) further showed that magnetic field strengths would have to be $10^9 < B_{field} \leq 10^{18}$ Tesla in order to induce a spacetime curvature (a geometrical measure of gravitational potential) of $10^9 > a_{curv} \geq 1$ meters, where a_{curv} is the radius of spacetime curvature. A pulsed-power field generator could be used to generate an electric or magnetic field driven propulsion. Puthoff et al. (2004) studied the Levi-Civita Effect within the context of the PV-GR model. They showed how the perturbation of the spacetime metric by the presence of uniform static magnetic and electric fields can be understood as a perturbation of the effective refractive index of the vacuum, and summarized in terms of its effect on the propagation of a light ray through the region containing the fields.

If the PV-GR model is correct, then modifying the vacuum index of refraction using electric or magnetic fields could induce a unique form of propulsion. Davis (2004) concluded that a dedicated research program would be necessary to develop and mature this propulsion concept.

4.3. Engineering the vacuum

The concept of “*engineering the vacuum*” had its genesis in the physics literature when it was introduced by Nobelist T.D. Lee in his textbook “*Particle Physics and Introduction to Field Theory*”, where he stated: “*The experimental method to alter the properties of the vacuum may be called vacuum engineering...If indeed we are able to alter the vacuum, then we may encounter new phenomena, totally unexpected*” (Lee, 1988). Comprehensive research has been done in this area by Puthoff (2010), noting that despite the extremely high energy requirements to restructure the spacetime metric to a significant degree, from such studies the signatures that would accompany advanced-technology craft can be outlined, and possible effects of the technology with regard to spacetime effects that include such phenomena as the distortion of space and time can be cataloged. As unbelievable as such features appear to be, they are totally in conformance with the principles of general relativity as presently understood. What remains as a challenge is to develop insight into the technological designs by which such vacuum restructuring can be generated on the scale required to implement the necessary spacetime modifications. Despite the challenges, sample calculations indicate the direction of potentially useful trends derivable on the basis of the application of GR principles as embodied in a metric engineering approach, with the results constrained only by what is achievable practically in an engineering sense. The latter is, however, a daunting constraint. At this point in the consideration of such nascent concepts, given our present level of technological evolution, it is premature to even guess at an optimum strategy, let alone attempt to form a critical path for the engineering development of such technologies. Nonetheless, only by inquiring into such concepts in a rigorous way can we hope to arrive at a proper assessment of the possibilities inherent in the evolution of advanced spaceflight technologies (Puthoff, 2010).

Variable	Typical Stellar Mass ($g_{00} < 1, g_{11} > 1$)	Spacetime-Engineered Metric ($g_{00} > 1, g_{11} < 1$)
Time Interval $\Delta t \rightarrow \Delta t / \sqrt{g_{00}}$	processes (e.g., clocks) run slower	processes (e.g., clocks) run faster
Frequency $\omega \rightarrow \omega \sqrt{g_{00}}$	red shift toward lower frequencies	blueshift toward higher frequencies
Energy $E \rightarrow E \sqrt{g_{00}}$	energy states lowered	energy states raised
Spatial measure $\Delta r \rightarrow \Delta r / \sqrt{-g_{11}}$	objects (e.g., rulers) shrink	objects (e.g., rulers) expand
Velocity of light $v_L = c \rightarrow c \sqrt{g_{00} / -g_{11}}$	effective $v_L < c$	effective $v_L > c$
Mass m $m = E/c^2$ $\rightarrow (-g_{11} / \sqrt{g_{00}}) m$	effective mass increases	effective mass decreases
Gravitational “force” $f(g_{00}, g_{11})$	“gravitational”	“antigravitational”

Table 2. *Metric Effects on Physical Processes in an Altered Spacetime as Interpreted by a Remote (Unaltered Spacetime) Observer.* (Puthoff, 2010)

As far as the time associated effects relevant for our present chapter, Puthoff (2010) notes that for an engineered spacetime associated with an advanced aerospace craft in which $\sqrt{g_{00}} > 1$, the time flow within the altered spacetime region would appear sped up to an external observer, while to an internal observer external time flow would appear to be in slow motion. In this scenario, close approach to such a craft could leave one with the impression of, say, a 20 minute time interval (corroborated by the observer’s watches), whereas only a few minutes would have passed in “real” or “normal” or “exterior” time. Conversely, for $\sqrt{g_{00}} < 1$ (typical stellar mass), an individual having spent time within such a temporally-modified field would, when returned to the normal environment, find that more time had passed in the “real” or “external” time than could be experientially accounted for. Another corollary would be that within the spacetime-altered region, normal environmental sounds from outside the region might cease to be registered, since external sounds could under these conditions redshift below the auditory range.

An additional implication of time speedup within the frame of such an exotic craft technology is that its flight path, which might seem precipitous from an external viewpoint (e.g., sudden acceleration or deceleration), would be experienced as much less so by the craft’s occupants. From the occupants’ viewpoint, observing the external environment to be in relative slow motion, it would not be surprising to consider that one’s relatively modest changes in motion would appear abrupt to an external observer (Puthoff, 2010). This could also explain the “darting” motions often observed with UFOs/UAPs and how inertial mass

could then be shielded from the consequences of the thousands of Gs that these craft seem to exhibit.

Another consequence of an accelerated time-frame due to craft associated metric engineering that leads to $\sqrt{g_{00}} > 1$, is that frequencies associated with the craft would for a remote observer appear to be blueshifted, which leads to the possibility that there would be a brightening of the craft's luminosity due to the heat spectrum blueshifting up into the visible portion of the spectrum. Additionally, close approach to such a craft could lead to possible harmful effects from ultraviolet and soft-X-ray generation due to blueshifting of the visible portion of the spectrum to higher frequencies. Very interesting effects associated with energy and spatial alterations are also mentioned, as follows.

For engineered spacetimes associated with advanced craft technology in which $\sqrt{g_{00}} > 1$ (accelerated time-frame case), a craft's material properties would appear "hardened" relative to the environment due to the increased binding energies of atoms in its material structure. Such a craft could, say, impact water at high velocities without apparent deleterious effects. A corollary is that the potential radiation exposure effects mentioned above would not be hazardous to craft occupants, since for those within the field of influence, the biological chemical bonds would be similarly hardened. An additional side effect potentially associated with exposure to the accelerated time-frame field would be accelerated aging of, say, plants in the area of a landed craft, and thus observation of the latter could act as a marker indicating the presence of such a field.

The fourth entry in Table 2 (spatial measure) indicates the size of an object within an altered spacetime region as seen by a remote observer. The size of, say, a spherical object is seen to have its radial dimension, r , scale as $1/\sqrt{-g_{11}}$, in the vicinity of a dense mass $\sqrt{-g_{11}} > 1$, in which case an object within the altered spacetime region appears to a remote observer to have shrunk. A consequence would be that metric engineering associated with an exotic craft to produce this effect could in principle result in a large craft with spacious interiors appearing to an external observer to be relatively small (Puthoff, 2010). This could serve to explain certain cases in which, allegedly, people taken on board these craft report that the inner dimensions are much larger than what can be observed from the outside.

Chapter V. Is consciousness the key?

There is anecdotal evidence, in the form of witness testimony, to suggest that at least some UFOs do not have elements or interfaces that would typically be associated with a spaceship, such as controls in the form of traditional buttons, levers, screens, cranks, etc; in many cases, only seats have been observed. If accurate, that poses the question of how might a pilot control the craft? We suggest that consciousness might play an important role, via some – as of yet unknown – interfaces or interactions between consciousness and the quantum vacuum zero-point field, that permeate the entirety of space and are non-local in nature. If that is true, then it is altogether not too difficult to envisage a means whereby a pilot would interface directly with the craft and the space-time around it, and cause it to move merely through a type of coherent thought output, of a sufficient intensity and frequency, that could tap into the ZPF and then “surf the wave” presumably indefinitely.

But first, what is even consciousness? This question has been an integral part of our existence since the very beginning; in fact, consciousness itself precedes the very first inquiry into its subject. It would seem in this case that consciousness is indeed the object from which all subjects arise.

"I regard consciousness as fundamental. I regard matter as derivative from consciousness. We cannot get behind consciousness. Everything that we talk about, everything that we regard as existing, postulates consciousness...All matter originates and exists only by virtue of a force which brings the particle of an atom to vibration and holds this most minute solar system of the atom together. We must assume behind this force the existence of a conscious and intelligent mind. This mind is the matrix of all matter."
[Max Planck]

There have been documented experiments involving consciousness that would indicate various “novel” phenomena which seem to have a dual relativistic – quantum nature where consciousness (energy) interacts, through the mind (physical), with the world of matter (which would be quantized, localized and “frozen” energy). Of these we will briefly list a few:

- Evidence for consciousness-related anomalies in random physical systems (Radin, Nelson; 1989)
- Long distance communication of binary symbols (Puthoff et. al., 1978)
- Multiple information transfer across spatial-temporal boundaries via non-ordinary channels of communication (Bisaha, 1978)
- Remote viewing of natural targets (Targ, Puthoff; 1974);
- Multiple subject and long-distance precognitive remote-viewing of geographical locations (Bisaha, Dunne; 1979)
- Laboratory research on a presumably PK-gifted subject (Gimeno and Burgo, 2017)
- Research into paranormal ability to break through spatial barriers (Kongzhi, Xianggao, Liangzhong; 1981, 1993)

Bearden (1979) notes that the present Cartesian interpretation of reality a priori excludes definitions of paranormal/parapsychological phenomena, since it recognizes only exclusively mental or exclusively physical states of phenomena. But much experimental and theoretical research seems to indicate that paranormal phenomena are inclusively quasi-mental and quasi-physical, in violation of the Cartesian assumption.

Remote viewing, a well documented “paranormal” phenomenon, refers to the acquisition and description, by mental means, of information blocked from ordinary perception by distance or shielding. Lee (2012) mentions that over 30 years of data has been gathered with statistically significant results frequently occurring under laboratory conditions, but that detractors are still not convinced that RV is a useful pursuit, noting that some of the output from RV can be vague and subject to personal interpretation. He concludes however that remote viewing and related processes merit further exploration and study and have the potential to make a meaningful contribution to the “professional futurist’s toolbox”. Incidentally, Dr. Gerd Gigerenzer, director of the Max Planck Institute for Human Development in Berlin, also indicates that intuitive wisdom often outperforms the calculations of experts.

Unexplained phenomena were always part of legends and traditions of many peoples around the world. They are also present now but, as a rule, the scientific community preferred to ignore them; usually on grounds of insufficient evidence. We can no longer claim lack of evidence. With so much evidence of events running contrary to our fundamental knowledge of physics, a major scientific effort should be undertaken to study them (Qingli Li, 1988). There would seem to be a wealth of solid experimental data on the subject of parapsychology, accumulated and published in China over the last decade; these publications should be translated into English but to justify translations, enough interest must be generated in the scientific community and, most of all, our attitudes must change (Qingli Li & Trzaska; ca. 1995). We should no longer laugh at phenomena we fail to understand. When myths and miracles become documented facts, they have to be treated as such.

*"You are not thinking, you are merely being logical."
[Niels Bohr]*

*"The tangible world is movement, say the Masters, not a collection of moving objects, but movement itself. There are no objects "in movement," it is the movement which constitutes the objects which appear to us: They are nothing but movement. This movement is a continued and infinitely rapid succession of flashes of energy. All objects perceptible to our senses, all phenomena of whatever kind and whatever aspect they may assume, are constituted by a rapid succession of instantaneous events."
[Alexandra David Neel & Llama Yongden]*

*"What nature asks of the apple-tree is that it shall bring forth apples, and of the pear-tree that it shall bring forth pears. Nature wants me to be simply man.
But a man conscious of what I am, and of what I am doing."
[Carl Gustav Jung]*

[Figure 17. Artistic representation of the body-consciousness field; Alex Grey, *Theologue*, 1986]

There have been relevant attempts to explain consciousness in scientific terms, in the form of, for example, the Monroe Institute's *Gateway Process*. We will attempt to go through some of the more important conclusions of the Gateway Process, in the context of a US INSCOM *Analysis and Assessment of the Gateway Process* (1983), as well as in the context of Itzhak Bentov's book, *Stalking the Wild Pendulum: On The Mechanics of Consciousness* (1977, 1988). Most of the subsequent content is reproduced in its original form, except where further details or references were added.

What is consciousness? It would be essential to define the mechanism by which the human mind could exercise the function known as consciousness, and to describe the way in which that consciousness operates to deduce meaning from the stimuli which it receives. The first point which needs to be made is that the two terms, matter and energy tend to be misleading if taken to indicate two distinctly different states of existence in the physical world that we know it. Indeed, if the term matter is taken to mean solid substance as opposed to energy which is understood to mean a force of some sort, then the use of the former is entirely misleading. Science now knows that both the electrons which spin in the energy field located around the nucleus of the atom and the nucleus itself are made up of nothing more than oscillating energy grids. Solid matter, in the strict construction of the term, does not exist. Rather, atomic structure is composed of oscillating energy grids surrounded by other oscillating energy grids which orbit at extraordinarily high speeds. In his book, *Stalking the Wild Pendulum*, Itzhak Bentov (1988) gives the following figures:

- The energy grid which composes the nucleus of the atom vibrates at approximately 10^{22} Hertz (which means 10 followed by 22 zeros). At 70 degrees Fahrenheit an atom oscillates at the rate of 10^{15} Hertz.
- An entire molecule, composed of a number of atoms bound together in a single energy field vibrates in the range of 10^9 Hertz. A live human cell vibrates at approximately 10^3 Hertz.

The point to be made is that the entire human being, brain, consciousness and all is, like the universe which surrounds him, nothing more or less than an extraordinarily complex system of energy fields. The so called states of matter are actually variances in the state of energy, and human consciousness is a function of the interaction of energy in two opposite states (motion vs rest) in a manner described as follows.

Energy creates, stores and retrieves meaning in the universe by projecting or expanding at certain frequencies in a three dimensional mode that creates a living pattern called a hologram. The concept of the hologram can be most easily understood by using Bentov's example where the reader visualizes a bowl full of water into which three pebbles are dropped. As the ripples created by the simultaneous entry of the three pebbles radiate outward towards the rim of the bowl, Bentov further asks the reader to visualize that the surface of the water is suddenly flash frozen so that the ripple pattern is preserved instantly. The ice is removed leaving the three pebbles still laying at the bottom of the bowl. Then the ice is exposed to a powerful, coherent source of light, such as a laser. The result will be a three dimensional model or representation of the position of the three pebbles suspended in midair. Holograms are capable of encoding so much detail that, for example, it is possible to take a holographic projection of a glass of swamp water and view it under magnification to see small organisms not visible to the naked eye when the glass of water itself is examined. The whole concept of holography, despite its scientific implications, has only been known to the physicist since the underlying mathematical principles were worked out by Dennis Gabor in 1947 (he later won a Nobel Prize for his work). Laboratory demonstration of Gabor's work only occurred years later following invention of the laser.

Of further importance is the fact that even if we dropped our frozen hologram of the ripple pattern on the floor, and broke it into a number of pieces, each individual piece would recreate the entire holographic image all by itself. The smaller the piece, the fuzzier and more distorted would be the resulting holographic projection, but the fact remains that a whole projection would nonetheless be made.

*"In the heaven of Indra there is said to be a network of pearls so arranged that if you look at one, you see all the others reflected in it."
[Hindu / Buddhist sutra]*

*"They [Buddhas] know all phenomena come from interdependent origination. They know all world systems exhaustively. They know all the different phenomena in all worlds, interrelated in Indra's net."
[Buddhāvataṃsaka sutra]*

Figure 18. Resonant bioelectromagnetic energy fields of human beings (Bentov, 1988).

The universe is composed of interacting energy fields, some at rest and some in motion. It is, in and of itself, one gigantic hologram of unbelievable complexity. According to the theories of Karl Pribram, a neuroscientist at Stanford University and David Bohm, a physicist at the University of London, the human mind is also a hologram which attunes itself to the universal hologram by the medium of energy exchange thereby deducing meaning and achieving the state which we call consciousness. With respect to states of expanded or altered consciousness such as Gateway uses, the process operates in the following way. As energy passes through various aspects of the universal hologram and is perceived by the electrostatic fields which comprise the human mind, the holographic images being conveyed are projected upon those electrostatic fields of the mind and are perceived or understood to the extent that the electrostatic field is operating at a frequency and amplitude that can harmonize with and therefore "read" the energy carrier wave pattern passing through it. Changes in the frequency and amplitude of the electrostatic field which comprises the human mind determines the configuration and hence the character of the holographic energy matrix which the mind projects to intercept meaning directly from the holographic transmissions of the universe. Then, to make sense of what the holographic image is "saying" to it, the mind proceeds to compare the image just received with itself. Specifically, it does this by comparing the image received with that part of its own hologram which constitutes memory.

Figure 19. The 'Cosmic Egg' model (Bentov, 1988).

Figure 20. Old Universe – New Universe model (Bentov,1988)

Fundamentally, the *Gateway Process* is a training system designed to bring enhanced strength, focus and coherence to the amplitude and frequency of brainwave output between the left and right hemispheres so as to alter consciousness, moving it outside the physical sphere so as to ultimately escape even the restrictions of time and space. The participant then gains access to the various levels of intuitive knowledge which the universe offers. What differentiates the *Gateway Process* from forms of meditation is its use of the *Hemi-Sync* technique which is defined in a monograph by Monroe Institute trainer Melissa Jager as, "a state of consciousness defined when the EEG patterns of both hemispheres are simultaneously equal in amplitude and frequency." Although Hemi-Sync seems to be rather rare and of only

short duration in ordinary human consciousness, Melissa Jager (of the Monroe Institute) states that: *"Audio techniques developed by Bob Monroe can induce and sustain Hemi-Sync with the Institute's basic Focus 3 tapes,..."*

She also notes that: *"Studies conducted by Elmer and Alyce Greene at the Menninger Foundation have shown that a subject with 20 years of training in Zen meditation could consistently establish Hemi-Sync at will, sustaining it for over 15 minutes."* Dr. Stuart Twemlow, a psychiatrist and a research associate of the Monroe Institute, reports that: *"In our studies of the effect of the Monroe tape system on brainwaves, we have found that the tapes encourage the focusing of brain energy (it can be measured as with a lightbulb, in watts) into a narrower and narrower 'frequency band'. This focusing of energy is not unlike the yoga concept of one pointedness, which we may translate in western terms as a Single-mindedness."*

Dr. Twemlow goes on to observe that as the individual gets into the tapes beyond Focus 3, *"...there is a gradual increase in brainwave size which is a measure of brain energy or power"*. Gateway assumes that once the frequency and amplitude of the human brain are rendered coherent, it is possible to begin accelerating both so that the human mind is soon resonating at ever higher vibrational levels. The mind can then bring itself into synchronization with more sophisticated and rarified energy levels in the universe. The mind, when operating at these increasingly rarified levels is assumed to be capable of processing the information thus received through the same fundamental matrix by which it makes sense of ordinary physical sensory input to achieve meaning in a cognitive context. Such meaning is usually perceived visually in the form of symbols but may also be perceived as astonishing flashes of holistic intuition or even in the form of scenarios involving both visual and 'aural' perception.

Figure 21. Earth-ionosphere capacitor (Bentov, 1988).

Figure 22. Sensory cortex "homunculus" (Bentov, 1988).

Figure 23. Lateral view (Bentov, 1988).

Figure 24. A view of the Third and Lateral Ventricles in the context of Associated Brain Structure (Bentov, 1977).

However, brain coherence through entrainment to "beat" frequencies introduced via stereo headphones is only part of the reason why the Gateway system works. It is also designed to achieve the physical quietude characteristic of deep transcendental meditative states which brings about a complete alteration of the fundamental resonance pattern associated with the sound frequencies produced by the human body. Yoga, zen or transcendental meditation, if practiced long enough, will produce a change in the sound frequency with which the human heart resonates throughout the entire body. According to Bentov, this change in resonance results from elimination of what the medical profession calls "the bifurcation echo" so that the sound of the heartbeat can move synchronously up and down the circulatory system in harmonious resonance approximately seven times a second.

Bentov describes the roll played by the bifurcation echo as follows: *"When the left ventricle of the heart ejects blood, the aorta, being elastic, balloons out just beyond the valve and causes a pressure pulse to travel down along the aorta. When the pressure pulse reaches the bifurcation in the lower abdomen (which is where the aorta forks in two to go into the legs), part of the pressure pulse rebounds and starts traveling up the aorta. If in the meantime the heart ejects more blood, and a new pressure pulse is traveling down, these two pressure points will eventually collide somewhere along the aorta and produce an interference pattern."* By placing the body in a sleeplike state, the Gateway tapes achieve the same goal as meditation in that it places the body in such a profoundly relaxed state that the bifurcation echo slowly fades away as the heart lessens the force and frequency with which it pushes blood into the aorta. The result is a regular, rhythmic sinewave pattern of sound which echoes throughout the body and rises up into the head in sustained resonance. The amplitude of this sinewave pattern, when measured with a sensitive, seismograph type instrument is about three times the average of the sound volume produced by the heart when it is operating normally.

Bentov's biomedical model shows that resonance is of considerable importance since it is directly transmitted to and impacts upon the brain. The resulting vibration is received and transmitted into the brain itself via the fluid filled third and left ventricles located above the brain stem. An electromagnetic pulse is then generated which stimulates the brain to raise the amplitude and frequency of brainwave output, just as Dr. Twemlow observed in his research on the effects of the Hemi-Sync tapes. Also, the brain is contained in a tight membrane called the *dura* which is, in turn, cushioned by a thin layer of fluid located between it and the skull. As the coherent resonance produced by the human heart in a state of profound relaxation reaches the fluid layer surrounding the brain, it sets up a rhythmic pattern in which the brain moves up and down approximately 0.005 to 0.010 millimeters in a continuous pattern. The self-reinforcing character of resonant behavior accounts for the body's ability to sustain this movement despite the minimal level of energy involved. In this way, the entire body, based on its own micromotion, functions as a tuned vibrational system which transfers energy in a range of between 6.8 and 7.5 Hertz into the earth's ionospheric cavity, which itself resonates at about 7-7.5 Hertz. Of this process, Bentov states:

"This is occurring at a very long wavelength of about 40,000 km, or just about the perimeter of the planet. In other words, the signal from the movement of our bodies will travel around the world in about one seventh of a second through the electrostatic field in which we are

imbedded. Such a long wavelength knows no obstacles, and its strength does not attenuate much over large distances. Naturally it will go through just about anything: metal, concrete, water, and the fields making up our bodies. It is the ideal medium for conveying a telepathic signal."

Consequently, the Gateway process is designed to rather rapidly induce a state of profound calm within the nervous system and to significantly lower blood pressure to cause the circulatory system, skeleton and all other physical organ systems to begin vibrating coherently at approximately 7-7.5 cycles per second (Hertz). The resulting resonance sets up a regular, repetitive sound wave which propagates in consonance with the electrostatic field of the earth.

As the body is turned into a coherent oscillator vibrating in harmony with the surrounding electrostatic medium, the specific exercises included in the Gateway tapes enjoin the participant to build up the energy field surrounding his body, presumably by using energy from the earth's field which the body is now entraining because of its ability to resonate with it. This puts the body's energy field into homogeneity with its surrounding environment and promotes movement of the seat of consciousness into the surrounding environment partly in response to the fact that the two electromagnetic medians are now a single energy continuum. Thus, the same process which moves the brain into focused coherence at steadily higher levels of frequency and amplitude so as to entrain analogous frequencies in the universe for data collection also promotes enhancement of bodily energy levels to a point adequate to permit the subject to experience an out-of-body movement when he is ready to do so (more will be said about this topic later). In addition, by resonating with the earth's electromagnetic sphere the human body creates a surprisingly powerful carrier wave to assist the mind in communication activity with other human minds similarly tuned.

"We could actually associate our whole reality with sound of one kind or another because our reality is a vibratory reality, and there is nothing static in it. Starting with the nucleus of an atom, which vibrates at enormous rates, the electrons and the molecules are all associated with characteristic vibratory rates. A most important aspect of matter is vibratory energy. When we think, our brains produce rhythmic electric currents. With their magnetic components, they spread out into space at the velocity of light, as do the electric waves or sounds produced by our hearts. They all mingle to form enormous interference patterns, spreading out and away from the planet. They are admittedly weak, but they are there. The more finely our systems are tuned, the clearer a signal we can pick out of the general noise of "sounds."

[Itzhak Bentov]

Figure 25. Model of reality as oscillating fields between rest and action (Bentov, 1988).

Up to this point, our discussion has been relatively simple and easy to follow. Now the fun begins. Gateway involves more than just perception of those aspects of the universal hologram which can be accessed in the dimension of time-space as we know it. To explain how and why human consciousness can be brought to transcend the limitations of time-space is the next task which must be addressed. To do this we must first appreciate what time and space are in order to understand how the dimension that they constitute can be transcended. Physicists define time as a measurement of energy of force in motion. In other words, it is a measurement of change. However, in order for energy to be in motion it must first be limited in some way within the confines of some sort of vibratory pattern so that its confinement gives it the capacity for being contained at a specific location which is distinguishable from other locations (space). Energy which is not confined is force without limit, without dimension, without the limits of form. It is infinity, cannot move because there is nothing beyond infinity, and is therefore outside of the dimension of time. It is also beyond space because that concept implies that a specific energy form is limited to a specific location, and is absent from other locations. But if energy is in the state of infinity, there are no boundaries, no "here" to differentiate from "there", no sense of area. Energy in infinity means energy uniformly extended without limit. It has no beginning, no end, no location. It is conscious force, the fundamental, primal power of existence without form, a state of infinite being.

Figure 26. Nonlinear representation of consciousness as a radiating pattern (Bentov, 1988).

Energy in infinity is said to be completely at rest and, therefore, cannot generate holograms so long as it remains utterly inactive. It retains its inherent capacity for consciousness in that it can receive and passively perceive holograms generated by energy in motion out in the various dimensions which make up the created universe put it cannot be perceived by consciousness operating in the active universe. Energy in this state of inactive infinity is termed by physicists as energy in its absolute state, or simply "the Absolute."

Between the Absolute and the "material" universe in which we experience our physical existence are various intervening dimensions to which human consciousness in altered states of being may gain temporary access. Theoretically, human consciousness may continue to expand the horizons of its perceptual capability until it reaches the dimension of the Absolute at which point perception may change character completely because the Absolute generates no holograms of or about itself.

Figure 27. Energy exchange between entities and the environment (Bentov, 1988).

Since the Absolute is conscious energy in infinity (i.e. without boundaries), it occupies every dimension to include the time-space dimension in which we have our physical existence but we cannot perceive it. It overlays everything as do many of the intervening gradients or dimensions through which the energies of the universe pass on their way to and from their home in the state of infinity (the absolute). To enter these intervening dimensions, human consciousness must focus with such intense coherence that the frequency of the energy pattern which comprises that consciousness (i.e. the brainwave output) can accelerate to the point where the resulting frequency pattern, if displayed on an oscilloscope, would look virtually like a solid line. Achievement of this state of altered consciousness sets the stage

for perception of non-time-space dimensions because of the operation of a principle in physics known as Planck's Distance.

This is an aspect of quantum mechanics which applies to the fact that any oscillating frequency (such as a brainwave) reaches two points of complete rest which constitute the boundaries of each individual oscillation (i.e. movement up or down). Without these points of rest, an oscillating wave pattern would be impossible since the points of rest are required to permit the energy to change direction and thus continue vibrating between rigid limits. But it is also true that when, for an infinitesimally brief instant, that energy reaches one of its two points of rest it "clicks out" of time-space and joins infinity. That critical step out of time-space occurs when the speed of the oscillation drops below 10^{-33} centimeters per second (Planck's Distance). To use the words of Bentov: "...quantum mechanics tell us that when distances go below Planck's Distance, which is 10^{-33} cm, we enter, in effect, a new world".

To return to our case in point, the human consciousness wave pattern reaches such high frequency that the pattern of "clickouts" comes so close together that there is virtual continuity in it. Then, a portion of that consciousness is actually postulated to establish and maintain its information collection function in those dimensions located between time-space and the Absolute. Thus, as the almost continuous "clickout" pattern establishes itself in continuous phase at speeds below Planck's Distance but before reaching the state of total rest, human consciousness passes through the looking glass of time-space after the fashion of Alice beginning her journey into wonderland. The Gateway process, with its associated Hemi-Sync technique, is apparently designed, if used systematically and patiently, to enable human consciousness to establish a coherent pattern of perception in those dimensions where speeds below Planck's distance apply. This holds true irrespective of whether the individual is exercising his consciousness while in his physical body or whether he is doing so after having separated that consciousness from the physical body (i.e. the so called out-of-body state).

Figure 28. Representation of the 'click-out' model (Bentov, 1977).

Much more could be reproduced here, but to do so would not be within scope of the present work. We will end the chapter here, with the acknowledgement that the United States Army Intelligence and Security Command's (INSCOM) *'Analysis and assesment of the Gateway Process'* (1983), and especially Itzhak Bentov's book *'Stalking the Wild Pendulum: On the Mechanics of Consciousness'* (1977, 1988) could potentially represent a very valuable resource and warrant further attention by anyone who would be interested in the study of consciousness.

Conclusions

In the first chapter we took a general look at what solid matter, light and nonlocality are and we noted that there are special circumstances in which the speed of light can be exceeded and that there are some real-life applications to such abstract concepts.

In the second chapter we looked at quantum vacuum zero-point energy and radiant energy, noting that space-time seems to be pervaded by a near-limitless source of energy that arises from fundamental interactions between matter and antimatter. We have also looked at a few practical applications of these technologies, some of which are in their infancy, but have great future potential.

In the third chapter we established a general framework for gravity and anti-gravity, as well as negative energy. We then looked at some of the theoretical concepts such as antigravity induced through negative energy and some practical examples of electrogravitics and electrokinetics.

In the fourth chapter we delved into space-time travel and what that might entail. We also noted theoretical methods of inducing space-time curvatures, such as engineering the vacuum and stargates or wormholes.

In the last chapter we attempted to describe consciousness as a fundamental aspect of space-time, noting the potentially dual energy-matter nature of consciousness, as well as delving into some available scientific and metaphysical concepts that would tend to support this hypothesis.

Many of the phenomena described here are of a quantum nature and therefore bound to be dismissed by many, but we would suggest that given the advent of instruments of extremely high voltage and extremely high frequency generation capabilities, many of these issues could be theoretically resolved. Quantum phenomena is generally described as only having a “noticeable” effect on space-time at the smallest scales, such as subatomic particles, but it is theorized that at extremely high energy levels, such as the Planck scale (10^{14} - 10^{19} GeV), the gravitational forces become comparable in effect to the electroweak force and the strong force, which should, if true, also be quite consequential for other quantum effects.

We acknowledge that highly advanced non-human intelligence is currently and generally not accepted scientifically, and agree to call this research purely hypothetical, until and if proven otherwise. This research is in no way meant as authoritative or comprehensive, but only as an introductory model of some of the available information that could be used to support a hypothetical framework for the physics of non-human intelligence.

Selected quotes

“Empiricism is unassailable on the fundamental ground of a pure logic; and its conclusions are equally impregnable. But if we look at it purely from a viewpoint of knowledge it leads into a blind alley, which is called solipsism. In order to escape from this impasse there is no other way open but to jump the wall at some part of it, and preferably at the beginning. This can be done only by introducing, once and for all, a metaphysical hypothesis which has nothing to do with the immediate experience of sense-perceptions or the conclusions logically drawn from them...the sense-impressions in our consciousness are not the only source of knowledge.”

“We have followed the call of common sense. We have taken a jump into the metaphysical realm; because we have accepted the hypothesis that sensory perceptions do not of themselves create the physical world around us, but rather that they bring news of another world which lies outside of ours and is entirely independent of us.”

“If the scope of physical science extends no further than the mere description of sensory experiences, then strictly only one’s own experiences can be taken as the object of such description; because only one’s own experiences are primary data. Now it is clear that on the basis of a mere individual complex of experience not even the most gifted of men could construct anything like a comprehensive scientific system. So, we are faced with the alternative of either renouncing the idea of a comprehensive science, which will hardly be agreed to even by the most extreme positivist, or to admit a compromise and allow the experiences of others to enter into the groundwork of scientific knowledge.”

“We see in all modern scientific advances that the solution of one problem only unveils the mystery of another. Each hilltop that we reach discloses to us another hilltop beyond. We must accept this as a hard-and-fast irrefutable fact... The aim of science... is an incessant struggle towards a goal which can never be reached. Because the goal is of its very nature unattainable. It is something that is essentially metaphysical and as such is always again and again beyond each achievement.”

Max Planck, 1933

“On the other hand, however, every one who is seriously engaged in the pursuit of science becomes convinced that the laws of nature manifest the existence of a spirit vastly superior to that of men, and one in the face of which we with our modest powers must feel humble. The pursuit of science leads therefore to a religious feeling of a special kind, which differs essentially from the religiosity of more naive people.”

Albert Einstein, 1936

“For a parallel to the lesson of atomic theory regarding the limited applicability of such customary idealizations, we must in fact turn to quite other branches of science, such as psychology, or even to that kind of epistemological problems with which already thinkers like Buddha and Lao Tzu have been confronted, when trying to harmonize our position as spectators and actors in the great drama of existence.”

“How wonderful that we have met with a paradox. Now we have some hope of making progress!”

Niels Bohr, 1937

"In how far we can understand the world around us is the ultimate thought of every student of nature. The coarseness of our senses prevents us from recognizing the ulterior construction of matter, and astronomy, this grandest and most positive of natural sciences, can only teach us something that happens, as it were, in our immediate neighborhood; of the remoter portions of the boundless universe, with its numberless stars and suns, we know nothing. But far beyond the limit of perception of our senses the spirit still can guide us, and so we may hope that even these unknown worlds — infinitely small and great — may in a measure become known to us. Still, even if this knowledge should reach us, the searching mind will find a barrier, perhaps forever unsurpassable, to the true recognition of that which seems to be, the mere appearance of which is the only and slender basis of all our philosophy."

Nikola Tesla, 1891

"Modern man knows that the Earth is only a ball suspended in a bottomless abyss and carried along in a dizzy and complex movement, and that this movement is governed by other celestial bodies incomparably larger than this Earth and situated at immense distances from it. He knows that the Earth on which he lives is but a grain of sand in comparison with the Sun, that the Sun itself is but a grain of sand amidst other incandescent stars, and that all is in motion. An irregularity in this assemblage of sidereal movements, an interference from a star foreign to our planetary system, a deviation of the Sun's trajectory, or any other cosmic accident, would suffice to make the Earth unsteady in its rotation, to trouble the course of the seasons, to change the atmosphere, and to destroy mankind. Modern man also knows that the smallest atom contains forces which, if unleashed, could involve the Earth in an almost instantaneous conflagration.

In spite of this, the man of our time lives and acts as if the normal and habitual operation of the rhythms of nature were something that was guaranteed to him. In actual practice, he thinks neither of the abysses of the stellar world nor of the terrible forces latent in every particle of matter. He sees the sky above him, with the Sun and the stars, as any child sees it, but the remembrance of the astronomical theories prevents him from recognizing in them divine signs. The sky for him is no longer the natural expression of the Spirit that enfolds and illuminates the world. Scientific knowledge has substituted itself for this "naive", yet profound vision, not as a new consciousness of a vaster cosmic order, an order of which man forms part, but as an estrangement, as an irremediable disarray before abysses that no longer have any common measure with him. For nothing now reminds him that in reality this whole Universe is contained within himself, not of course in his individual being, but in the Spirit or intellect which is within him, and which is both greater than himself and the whole phenomenal Universe."

Titus Burckhardt, 1987

"Modern man does not understand how much his "rationalism" (which has destroyed his capacity to respond to numinous symbols and ideas) has put him at the mercy of the psychic "underworld." He has freed himself from "superstition" (or so he believes), but in the process he has lost his spiritual values to a positively dangerous degree. His moral and spiritual tradition has disintegrated, and he is now paying the price for this break-up in worldwide disorientation and dissociation."

Carl Gustav Jung, 1964

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which are used in all fighters, cannot be so inaccurate that the information obtained with them can be doubted completely.”

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